

Assessing the Impact of Financial Development on Economic Growth in Ghana: an Empirical Evidence from 1992 to 2017 Using Multivariate Regression and Regression with Newey-West Standard Errors

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Abstract

The study examines the impact of financial development on economic growth in Ghana in a time-series study from 1992 to 2017. The study employed time-series methodologies such as multivariate regression and regression with Newey-west standard errors. The study concludes that domestic credit to the private sector (financial development) has a direct relationship or strong positive impact on economic growth in Ghana, but trade openness has a negative impact on economic growth meanwhile unemployment rate, inflation, and regulatory quality have an insignificant impact on economic growth in Ghana in the sample period. Moreover, the study recommends that the government should strengthen its efforts in creating the enabling environment to facilitate the provision of domestic credit to the private sector by the financial sector and also create avenues for easy accessibility of credit domestically due to its strong impact on economic growth

Keywords: Financial development; Economic growth; Multivariate regression; Regression with Newey-West standard errors; Ghana

1. Introduction

Economic growth is the major tool to measure the performance of every economy hence the use of real GDP growth annually to make such estimations. Financial development has been considered as one of the strong or major determinants of economic growth in many previous studies (G. Adu et al., 2013). Literature from Levine (2004) contributes to financial development which he established that financial development consists of the advancement of (i) fabrication of “ex ante” information about potential investment, (ii) supervising of investments and execution of corporate governance, (iii) commerce, diversification, and risk management, (iv) organization and bringing together of savings and (v) swapping of goods and services. All of these functions could influence savings and investment advisory decisions which could otherwise contribute to economic growth.

Some theorists shared earlier contributions to the finance and economic growth nexus (Schumpeter, 1911; Robinson, 1952; Patrick, 1966; Goldsmith, 1969; Mckinnon, 1973; Shaw, 1973). According to these prolific researchers, a well and highly functioning financial sector could propagate technological advancements and innovations as a result of efficient and effective allocation of resources from the inefficient and ineffective sectors to the efficient and effective sectors productively. Also, the development of a firm and strong financial sector can propagate economic growth which is the assertion of the “Supply-leading hypothesis” proposed by Patrick (1966). Moreover, the enlargement of the financial sector to increase economic growth will lead to an increase in demand for services from the financial markets. This development will bolster the growth in the financial markets and their services which will foster growth in the non-financial sector along with the growth in the other economic sectors through intermediation between the deficit units and surplus units by enticing investments with high rate of returns.

G. Adu et al. (2013) studied financial development and its impact on growth in Ghana; they argue that the effect of financial development on economic depends on the kind of proxy measure of financial development. However, as financial development can be measured by domestic credit to the private sector and broad money stock/GDP ratio; they found that domestic credit to private sector in Ghana has direct impact on economic

growth unlike broad money stock/GDP ratio which according to their study confirmed an inverse relationship. Apparently, they share the opinion that the measure of financial development should be cautiously considered in the finance and economic growth nexus. Chee-Keong& Chan (2011) also found that domestic credit to private sector has a direct impact on economic growth.

Prior studies on finance-growth nexus have mixed findings. Thus, there is not one direction of the argument about the subject-matter. However, some previous studies are of the opinion that financial development has direct or positive impact on economic growth and others have diverse opinion (Lucas, 1988; Gelb, 1989; King & Levine, 1993a, 1993b; Demetriades& Hussein, 1996; Neusser&Kugler, 1998; Wang, 1999; Levine et al., 2000; Khan &Senhadji, 2000; Khan, 2008; Quartey&Prah, 2008; Khan, 2008; Kargbo&Adamu, 2009; Odhiambo, 2009; Chee-Keong& Chan, 2011; G. Adu et al., 2013).

In Ghana, studies on the impact of financial development on economic growth are very limited (Quartey&Prah, 2008; G. Adu et al., 2013; Ezzo, 2010), in this regard stems the study's motivation to assess the impact of financial development on economic in Ghana.Also, it will contribute to the few existing kinds of literature on the finance-growth nexus in Ghana for academic use and policy formulation guide.

The rest of the study comprises of part 2 containing the data and methodology; part 3 consists of empirical results and findings discussion. Part 4 concludes the study and proposes some recommendations.

2. Data and Methodology

2.1 Data

The study used data sourced from World Banks' Global Financial Development Database and Worldwide Governance Indicators from 1992 to 2017. The study uses seven variables to pursue its objective of assessing the impact of financial development on economic growth in Ghana. The dependent variable for the study is the gross domestic product per capita as a proxy measure of economic growth and the independent variables considered as proxies' measure of financial development are the domestic credit to the private sector and the domestic credit provided by banks. However, to control for the macroeconomic factors that could affect the function of financial development and economic growth; some variables are considered to that effect. The control or intervening variables that the study considered are inflation, trade openness, unemployment and regulatory quality. Further details about the variables can be found in table 1.

Table 1 Variables description

Variable Name	Description	Source
Indcp	Domestic credit to the private sector (% of GDP)	Global financial development
Inggdppc	GDP per capita (constant 2010 US\$)	Global financial development
Indcban	Domestic credit to the private sector by banks (% of GDP)	Global financial development
Ininf	Inflation, consumer prices (annual %)	Global financial development
Intrade	Trade (% of GDP)	Global financial development
Inunemp	Unemployment, total (% of the total labor force) (ILO est.)	Global financial development
regqty	Regulatory quality	Worldwide Governance Indic.

2.2 Methodology

The study employed time series methodologies hence the use of group unit root test, correlation matrix, cointegration test, multivariate regression, regression with Newey-west standard errors and granger causality test.

The first step that the study undertakes is to compute the descriptive statistics of the data or variables to ascertain the mean, the median, minimum and maximum values of the variables. Moreover, the tests of

Skewness, Kurtosis, Jarque-Bera, standard deviation and test for equality of means are executed to ensure the accuracy of the data for further applications. Furthermore, the unit root test is employed to ensure the stationary status of the variables in order not to run a bogus regression. The tests of Levin et al. (2002), Maddala and Wu (1999) and Im et al. (2003) are used in this regard to assess the stationarity level of the variables to reject the null hypothesis that none of the variables is stationary. When it is ascertained that there is evidence of stationary hence no unit root then the next step is to test multicollinearity among the independent variables. The correlation matrix is used to find out whether there is an evidence of multicollinearity in the variables. Cointegration test becomes the next step after it has been proven that there is no evidence of multicollinearity. The cointegration test is performed to find out the “long-run relationship or equilibrium” between the dependent variable and the independent variables. Evidence of significance in the test confirms cointegration relationship or long-run relationship hence the coefficients that will be reported by the regression models will be the long run results or relationships between the dependent and independent variables. After the cointegration test, the next step is to regress the independent variables on the dependent variables to ascertain the coefficients of causal relationships; hence the use of a multivariate regression method. Multivariate regression is used due to the reason that there are multiple independent variables or regressors. However, to ensure the robustness of the results that will be produced by the multivariate regression model; the study also employs regression with Newey-west standard errors for a robust check. Regression with Newey-west standard errors assesses the variance where autocorrelation is present as well as heteroskedasticity. This regression method can solve the problem of autocorrelation and heteroskedasticity.

Finally, the study performs a granger causality test to discover the causal relationship or linkage between the independent and dependent variables. The result is expected to confirm either unidirectional or bidirectional causality or linkage in order to reject the null hypothesis, which posits that there is no evidence of Granger causality among the variables.

Model specification

The econometric model for the study can be written as follows:

Equation 1

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_k X_k + \varepsilon$$

Equation 2

Economic growth = f(financial development, inflation, trade, unemployment, regulatory quality)

In the above equation (1), Y represents the dependent variable, β_0 represents regression coefficient of the intercept/constant, $\beta_1 X_1 \rightarrow \beta_k X_k$ represents the regressors and the coefficients, or independent variables and ε represents the stochastic error term or disturbance that cannot be estimated for by the independent variables. The variables were transformed into their natural logarithm to avoid fluctuations in the data series except for regulatory quality variable and the model for the study can now be written as:

Equation 3

$$\ln gdp pc = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \left(\frac{\ln dc p}{\ln dc p bank} \right) + \beta_2 (\ln inf) + \beta_3 (\ln trade) + \beta_4 (\ln uemp) + \beta_5 (reg qty) + \varepsilon$$

In the equation (3), $\ln gdp pc$ is the dependent variable and represents log of gross domestic product per capita as proxy measure of economic growth, $\ln dc p$ and $\ln dc p bank$ represent domestic credit to private sector and domestic credit to private sector by banks; they are the proxies measure of financial development, $\ln inf$

represents inflation, \lntrade represents trade openness, \lnunemp represents unemployment rate and $regqty$ represents regulatory quality. β_0 represents the intercept and ε represents the error term.

3. Empirical results and findings discussion

3.1 Descriptive statistics

Table 2 displays the descriptive or summary statistics of the variables and from the table, it can be reported that $\ln gdpcc$ thus proxy measure of economic growth has a mean value of 7.046 which literally means that economic growth over the same period of 1992 to 2017 grew at an annual average of 7.046% with a minimum rate of 6.748% and a maximum rate of 7.471%. Domestic credit provided to the private by the entire financial sector had an annual average increase of 2.466% with a minimum rate of 1.577% and a maximum rate of 3.031%. Moreover, domestic credit to private sectors by banks increased at a year on year average rate of 2.390% with a minimum rate of 1.577% and a maximum rate of 2.762%. Taking into account inflation, inflation increased during the sample period at an average rate of 2.830%, unemployment rate and trade openness increased at an average year on year rate of 1.865% and 4.335% respectively. However, the standard deviations report homogenous relationships among the variables and the Jarque-Bera test confirms that all the variables are in normal distribution except $\ln dcpbank$. In table 2, the results of the test of equality of means can be found beneath and from the results, it can be evidenced that the results of the Anova and Welch tests confirm significance.

Table 2 Descriptive statistics

	$\ln gdpcc$	$\ln dcp$	$\ln dcpbank$	$\ln inf$	$\ln trade$	$\ln unemp$	$regqty$
Mean	7.046	2.466	2.390	2.830	4.335	1.865	-0.071
Median	6.978	2.608	2.537	2.728	4.311	1.867	-0.019
Maximum	7.471	3.031	2.762	4.085	4.754	2.338	0.128
Minimum	6.748	1.577	1.577	1.964	3.829	1.518	-0.448
Std. Dev.	0.241	0.461	0.400	0.511	0.224	0.234	0.155
Skewness	0.489	-0.876	-1.146	0.669	-0.053	0.358	-0.902
Kurtosis	1.783	2.494	2.770	2.992	2.546	2.393	3.001
Jarque-Bera	2.639	3.604	5.749	1.941	0.236	0.953	3.525
Probability	0.267	0.165	0.056	0.379	0.889	0.621	0.172
Obs.	26	26	26	26	26	26	26

Test for Equality of Means Between Series			
Method	df	Value	Probability
ANOVA F-test	(6, 175)	1093.481***	0.000
Welch F-test*	(6, 76.5246)	2930.866***	0.000

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level

3.2 Group unit root test

The study performed unit root test to confirm stationary among the variables hence the use of Levin, Lin & Chu test, Im-Pesaran & Shim test, ADF-Fisher, and PP-Fisher tests to prove otherwise. The outcome of the tests can be found in table 3; from the table, it can be found that at level form the variables showed stationary with ADF-Fisher and PP-Fisher tests but not with Levin, Lin & Chi and Im-Pesaran tests. Furthermore, the study continued the test in the first difference and at first difference, all the tests became stationary at 1% significance level confirming the absence of unit root hence the rejection of the null hypothesis that there is evidence of unit root in the variables.

Table 3 Group unit root tests

Method	Statistic	Prob.**	sig.	Cross-sections	Obs
Level form					
Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-0.069	0.473		7	171
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-1.176	0.120		7	171
ADF - Fisher Chi-square	22.457	0.070	*	7	171
PP - Fisher Chi-square	25.088	0.034	**	7	175
First difference					
Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-5.201	0.000	***	7	164
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-7.265	0.000	***	7	164
ADF - Fisher Chi-square	75.731	0.000	***	7	164
PP - Fisher Chi-square	109.070	0.000	***	7	168

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level, * indicates 10% significance level

3.3 Correlation matrix

To check for multicollinearity in the variables, the study computed the correlation matrix to reveal the truth. Table 4 reports the outcome of the correlation matrix and from the table, it is evidenced that there is no presence of multicollinearity. The rule of thumb posits that two independent variables should not have correlation coefficients of ± 0.70 with the dependent variables. According to table 4, the highest correlation coefficient is 0.821 and the second highest is 0.671. Therefore, the study confidently infers that there is no evidence of multicollinearity. However, the independent variables have a positive correlation with the dependent variable; thus Indcp has a correlation coefficient of 0.821 with lngdppc and Indcpbank has a correlation coefficient of 0.671 with lngdppc. Also, inflation has a negative correlation with economic growth at 10% significance level with a correlation coefficient of -0.510. To account for Intrade, lnumep and regqty, they all showed insignificant correlation with lngdppc.

Table 4 Correlation matrix

Correlation	lngdppc	Indcp	Indcpbnk	lninf	Intrade	lnumep	regqty
Probability							
lngdppc	1						
Indcp	0.821***	1					
Indcpbank	0.671***	0.961***	1				
lninf	-0.510*	-0.501*	-0.506*	1			
Intrade	0.000	0.419**	0.547**	0.016	1		
lnumep	-0.177	0.076	0.071	0.342*	0.624***	1	
regqty	0.245	0.054	0.038	-0.232	-0.298	-0.324	1

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level, * indicates 10% significance level

3.4 Cointegration test

The study computed the cointegration test to find out the long-run relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables. According to the results of the cointegration test, there is evidence of cointegration or long-run relationship between the independent and dependent variables. From all indications,

the trace and max-eigen tests showed significance from None to At most 3, confirming that there is a long-run relationship between the variables. Results can be found in table 5.

Table 5Cointegration test

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)				
Hypothesized	Trace	0.05		
No. of CE(s)	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**	
None *	227.641	125.615	0.000	***
At most 1 *	153.386	95.754	0.000	***
At most 2 *	94.198	69.819	0.000	***
At most 3 *	55.553	47.856	0.008	**
At most 4	25.895	29.797	0.132	
At most 5	13.055	15.495	0.113	
At most 6	1.222	3.841	0.269	
Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)				
Hypothesized	Max-Eigen	0.05		
No. of CE(s)	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**	
None *	74.256	46.231	0.000	***
At most 1 *	59.188	40.078	0.000	***
At most 2 *	38.645	33.877	0.013	**
At most 3 *	29.659	27.584	0.027	**
At most 4	12.839	21.132	0.467	
At most 5	11.833	14.265	0.117	
At most 6	1.222	3.841	0.269	

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level, * indicates 10% significance level

3.5 Assessing the impact of financial development on economic growth

The study’s objective is to assess the impact of financial development on economic growth, specifically in Ghana. However, the study employed multivariate regression and regression with Newey-west standard errors for its data analysis. Table 6 exhibits the results and from the table, it can be reported that financial development has a positive and statistically significant impact on economic growth at 1% significance level. Considering the two proxies measure of financial development, Indcp showed a coefficient of 0.516 and Indcpbank also showed a coefficient of 0.585 across the two regression methods used for the study. The results signal that a percentage increase in the financial development of Ghana will lead to a 0.516% and 0.585% increase in economic growth respectively. Perhaps, inflation, unemployment rate, and regulation quality showed an insignificant impact on economic growth. Moreover, trade openness showed a negative and statistically significant impact on economic growth at 5% significance level across the two methods. With coefficients of -0.437 and -0.674, a percentage increase in trade openness will lead to 0.437% and 0.674% decrease in economic growth.

The results of the regression with Newey-west standard errors share the same coefficients with the multivariate regression method which strongly confirms the validity of the results provided by the study's main model; regression with Newey-west standard errors was used for robust check. With regards to the model fitness of the two models, the F-statistics of all the models showed 1% significance and the r-squared of the multivariate regression was fairly good to confirm the fitness of the models and appropriateness of the results.

Table 6 Regression results: Multivariate regression and Regression with Newey-west standard errors

	Multivariate		Newey-west standard errors	
lninf	-0.000 (-0.00)	-0.027 (-0.34)	-0.000 (-0.00)	-0.027 (-0.32)
Intrade	-0.437 (-2.90)**	-0.674 (-2.77)**	-0.437 (-2.74)**	-0.674 (-2.49)**
lnumep	0.027 (0.19)	0.192 (0.99)	0.027 (0.14)	0.192 (0.68)
regqty	0.124 (0.78)	0.107 (0.48)	0.124 (0.82)	0.107 (0.57)
Indcp	0.516 (7.86)***		0.516 (8.88)***	
Indcpbank		0.585 (4.77)***		0.585 (4.84)***
constant	7.627 (14.84)***	8.298 (11.35)***	7.627 (17.52)***	8.298 (11.96)***
R-squared	0.824	0.663		
F-statistics	18.670***	7.873***	30.27***	10.89***

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level. T-statistics are in parentheses.

3.6 Granger causality test

To confirm the direction of causality and linkage, the study performed a granger causality test to unravel the evidence of Granger causality. In brief, the null hypothesis of the granger causality states that there is no evidence of Granger causality among the variables. At this juncture, the study ensures to either reject or accept the null hypothesis. Table 7 displays the outcome of the granger causality test and it is evidenced that there is no evidence of bidirectional Granger causality, but there is evidence of unidirectional Granger causality. The unidirectional granger causality evidence stems from economic growth to inflation, domestic credit to the private sector to inflation, domestic credit to the private sector by banks to inflation, inflation to regulatory quality, unemployment rate to trade openness and unemployment rate to regulatory quality. The evidence of unidirectional linkage or granger causality simply means that a change in the first variables causes a change in the latter variables but not vice versa. To conclude, the study rejects the null hypothesis that there is no granger causality among the variables.

Table 7 Granger causality test

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	
lngdppc does not granger cause lninf	24	2.936	0.077	*
Indcp does not granger cause lninf	24	3.231	0.062	*
Indpcbnk does not granger cause lninf	24	3.888	0.038	**
lninf does not granger cause regqty	24	2.888	0.080	*
lnumep does not granger cause Intrade	24	4.015	0.035	**
lnumep does not granger cause regqty	24	3.651	0.046	**

Note: * indicates 10% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level.

4. Conclusion

The study assessed the impact of financial development on economic growth in Ghana from 1992 to 2017 and the data used were sourced from World Bank's Global Financial Development Database and Worldwide Governance Indicators. The study used time-series methodologies such as group unit root test, correlation matrix, cointegration test, multivariate regression, regression with Newey-west standard errors and granger causality test.

The study concludes that financial development has a strong and positive impact on economic growth while trade openness has a negative impact on economic growth in Ghana. To account for inflation, unemployment rate, and regulatory quality, they all have an insignificant impact on economic growth in Ghana.

The study recommends that it will be beneficial if the government strengthens its efforts to allow the financial sector to provide domestic credit to the private sector and also initiate avenues for easy accessibility of credit domestically due to its strong impact on economic growth. To buttress this recommendation, it is assumed that credits provided to the private sector domestically are largely from the indigenes hence no threat of repatriation of funds invested into the economy which could not allow time for borrowers to leverage on the credits provided to them hence short term credit facilities. To buttress this recommendation, it is assumed that credits provided to the private sector domestically are largely from the indigenes hence no threat of repatriation which could not allow time for borrowers to leverage on the credits provided to them.

The study recommends future research into the area of financial development and economic growth with an emphasis on the industrial structure of the economy and other external factors that can affect financial development.

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